

Buckling Analysis of The Composite Column by Using Finite Element Method And Experimental Method

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Abstract :

In this study, the buckling analysis of the square column made from unidirectional composite of glass fiber – epoxy matrix, kevlar fiber – epoxy matrix and carbon fiber – epoxy matrix and for different ratios of width to length (h/l) has been carried out using finite element analysis and experimentally.

Buckling analysis illustrate that the critical load from finite element analysis was higher than that obtained experimentally and the maximum difference was (16.5 %) for carbon fiber – epoxy matrix composite at ($h/l = 0.05$).

The results show that the critical load ($P_{cr} = 1480$ N) at ($h/l = 0.02$) and ($P_{cr} = 57830$ N) at ($h/l = 0.05$) for glass fiber- epoxy matrix composite.

Also the results illustrated that the critical load depends on the type of the composite material where the ($P_{cr} = 1310$ N) for glass fiber-epoxy matrix and ($P_{cr} = 6333$ N) for carbon fiber-epoxy matrix composite.

الخلاصة :

في هذه الدراسة، تم دراسة تحليل الانبعاج لدعامات ذات مقطع مربع مصنوعة من مادة مركبة أحادية الاتجاه من مواد مختلفة مثل اليفاف الزجاج - والأساس ايبوكسي واليفاف الكفلر - والأساس ايبوكسي واليفاف الكربون - والأساس ايبوكسي ولنسب مختلفة من العرض الى الطول (h/l) باستخدام الطريقة العملية وطريقة العناصر المحددة.

يبين تحليل الانبعاج بأن الحمل الحرج المستخرج من طريقة العناصر المحددة يكون أعلى من المستخرج من الطريقة العملية وأعلى فرق كان (16.5 %) للدعامات المصنوعة من اليفاف الكربون - والأساس ايبوكسي عند نسبة ($h/l = 0.05$).

بينت النتائج بان الحمل الحرج ($P_{cr}=1480$ N) عند ($h/l=0.02$) و ($P_{cr} = 57830$ N) عند ($h/l=$ 0.05) لدعامات مصنوعة اليفاف الزجاج - والأساس ايبوكسي.

كذلك بينت النتائج بان الحمل الحرج يعتمد على نوع المادة المركبة حيث ان ($P_{cr} = 1310$ N) لمادة مركبة مصنوعة من اليفاف الزجاج - والأساس ايبوكسي و ($P_{cr} = 6333$ N) لمادة مركبة مصنوعة من اليفاف الكربون - والأساس ايبوكسي.

Introduction :

Buckling in the general term frequently used to describe the failure of structures between stable and unstable case.

When the magnitude of the load on a structure is such that the equilibrium is changed from stable to unstable the load is called a critical load (or buckling load) [1].

Buckling happen to the longer beam, bar, wide plate and thin cylindrical shell,...etc. made from isotropic material or orthotropic material (composite material) with single layer or multi layers. Therefore the buckling depends on the shape (dimension) of the component (i.e ratio of thickness to length) and the material properties.

In this problem the column is made from three different composite materials as follows: Kevlar fiber-epoxy matrix composite material, carbon fiber-epoxy matrix composite material and glass fiber-epoxy matrix composite material. The effects of different variables such as (h/l) and fiber volume fraction (V_f) on the buckling of the composite square column have been studied both experimentally and by using finite element method. Some of the applications of column are the post and turret of boats, structural building, and wing of satellite space land....etc.

The aim of this work is to investigate buckling (critical load and first critical mode of buckling) of the square composite column which is made from different composite materials. different ratios of (h/l) , and different fiber volume fractions by means of the finite element analysis. It is also intended to conduct an experimental program to confirm the finite element analysis results.

Most of the work concentrated on determining the critical buckling loads of the square column with various loading bounding conditions. The subject was taken both numerically and experimentally. The equations of the buckling of the square column have been derived many years ago and readily a variable to design engineers [2].

Beam-columns made of polymer-matrix fiber reinforced composite materials are increasingly being used in automotive, aerospace, structural and mechanical engineering industries. And buckling loads are of important parameter in the design and development of high-performance composite.

R.Ganesan [3] determined the mean value of buckling loads of the beam made from polymer (epoxy) matrix and fiber (carbon) reinforced composite material.

Tai-Kuang Lee [4] proposes a reliable and computationally efficient beam-column finite element model for the analysis of composite columns under uniaxial bending

and axial force. And make comparison between the model and empirical data. Also found that the buckling of the longitudinal reinforcement appears to be the main cause leading to severe decay of fully encased composite beam-columns.

Carol K. [5] study the buckling of polymeric composite beam and make comparing between buckling loads of rectangular cross section beams modeled by present theory to the loads obtained by a plate buckling analysis, and found excellent agreement is shown between plate buckling and the beam analysis.

Pulmono [6] study the collapse loads of reinforced concrete beam with large openings is cast as a mathematical programming problem using the static theorem of plasticity. The mathematical programming methods are ideally suited for finding the collapse loads of a wide range of suitably discretized structural systems.

Thompson, P. [7] studied the deformation occurring in open-section composite beams. And the major verification resulting from this study is that the shear center of an open section composite beam can be altered. Also, it was observed that the choice of the material system dose not have an effect on the amount of deformation.

Lindberg and Florence [8] published summarized results from research on buckling of metal cylinders under different types of loading.

Pegg [9] investigated numerically of dynamic pulse buckling of cylinders of infinite length and different radius to thickness ratios. He also examined the effect of the pulse duration and the combination of static and impulsive dynamic loading.

Shawetal [10] presented results from numerical solution of fiber reinforced composite cylindrical subjected to axial and torsional impulsive loads.

Zdenek Po Bazant and walter PoMurphy [11], Studied the theory of collapse of the world trade center towers was not due to the horizontal impact of the aircraft but it was due to the buckling effect. More than about half of the columns in critical floor were buckled due to heat see figure (1).

The vertical impact of the upper part falling onto the lower part generated vertical loads much higher than the load capacity in the columns of the underlying floor (stage 4). The columns of the lower floor thus buckle too progressive. Buckling under subsequent dynamic impacts then proceeds downward floor by floor.

Theoretical analysis :

The buckling analysis of the beam-column made from polymer-matrix fiber-reinforced composite materials have been interested here because the beam-columns have a wide range of application in automotive, aerospace, structural, and mechanical engineering industries.

The buckling analysis is a technique used to determine the critical load of the column of which the column becomes unstable. And that depend on their material (matrix, fiber), geometric and structural properties [12].

In the static analysis of perfect structures, the tow phenomena loosely termed" buckling" are: 1-) Collapse at the maximum point in a load vs deflection curve (nonlinear), and 2-) Bifurcation buckling .

The collapse (no linear) buckling analysis is usually more accurate approach and it is structures. While the linear (Eigen value) buckling analysis predicts the theoretical buckling strength (the bifurcation point) of an ideal linear elastic structure.

Therefore Buckling is generally term frequently used to describe the failure of a structural element when a portion of the element moves normal to the direction of the primary load application and this load may be (compression, shear, torsion, etc.) [13].

Consider an ideal straight, prismatic column composed and subjected to an axial compressive load with dimensions as shown in figure (2).

If the column is ideal, then it will remain straight under all levels of load F. suppose that the column is subjected to a slight lateral disturbance as the load is increased from zero for low levels of axial load, when the disturbance is removed, the column will return to the straight condition. However, at certain critical value of the axial load, a slight disturbance will result in very large lateral deflection of the column and the column will remain in the deflected condition even through the disturbance is removed. This critical load, called the Euler buckling load, is given by :

$$P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E.I}{L^2} \dots\dots (1)$$

Where

E = Young's Modulus

I = Moment of Inertia

L= Length of column

It is used for case of column with hinged ends as shown in figure (3) [14].

There are three different of failure of the column which depend on the geometry (slenderness ratio) of the member and the properties of the materials:

1. The failure of a short compression member, resulting from the compression axial force.
2. The failure of a long compression member, for a long column, buckling occurs way before the normal stress reaches the strength of the column material.
3. The failure of an intermediate length compression member, kneeling occurs when some area yield before buckling.

Here buckling can be calculated by two methods:

- 1-) Practically by testing the sample of column under various axial load and determine the critical load of the composite material.
- 2-) By the introducing of computers , this method based on program analysis called (ANSYS) can calculate the critical load of a composite material more precisely.

Composite materials:

Column specimens are made from composite material which consist of continuous medium called matrix and discontinuous medium called reinforcement, which is usually harder and stronger.

Composite material of the column is orthographic material has a material properties that is different in three mutually perpendicular directions at a point of the body.

The rule of mixtures always predicts the elastic constant of the composite material.

The elastic constants of a fiber-reinforced composite must be determined in terms of the properties of the fiber and the matrix and in terms of the relative volumes of fiber and matrix: [15].

$$E_{ij} = f (E_f, \nu_f, V_f, E_m, \nu_m, v_m) \quad (2)$$

Where:

$$V_f = \frac{\text{Volume of fibers}}{\text{Total volume of composite}}$$

With analogous definitions applying for the matrix material:

$$V_m = \frac{\text{Volume of matrix}}{\text{Total volume of composite}}$$

$$V_f + V_m = 1 \quad (3)$$

Modulus of elasticity in the longitudinal direction:

$$E_l = E_f \cdot V_f + E_m \cdot V_m \quad (4)$$

Where

E_f, E_m - Modulus of elasticity of fiber and matrix material respectively.

V_f, V_m - Volume fraction of fiber and matrix material respectively.

Modulus of elasticity in the lateral direction:

$$E_2 = \frac{E_f \cdot E_m}{E_f \cdot V_m + E_m \cdot V_f} \quad (5)$$

Composite materials behave in a different manner from that of one-element material. This difference may be viewed by buckling value and it may be higher or lower than that of one-element material according to the rule of mixture.

Finite Element Analysis :

Therefore, the finite element method has become a powerful tool for the numerical solution of a wide range of engineering problems. In 1970, the finite element method becomes more affect used in a wide range to solving the numerical engineering problem [16].

The ANSYS package is used here in the buckling analysis of the beam made from composite under axial loading to determine the critical loads at which the structure becomes unstable.

The column is constructed of orthotropic material with the different length and different cross-sectional area.

Modeling :

For the finite element method analysis of the buckling of the column problem, the ANSYS 5.4 package program is adopted. This program has very efficient capabilities to perform finite element analysis of most engineering problem . The column is treated

as a composite square column with different material properties and different dimensions of the column.

The following steps represent the procedure of modeling the problem:-

(1-) Build the model

In this step made definition to the element types, element real constants, material properties, and the model geometry. Due to symmetry only lower half of the column is modeled. The boundary conditions become fixed-free for half symmetry modal as shown in figure (4).

(2-) Applied loads and obtain the static solution

In this step defined the analysis type and options, applied load (displacement and force), specify load step options, meshing of the problem and begin the finite element solution.

(3-) Obtain the eigen value buckling solution

This step requires files from the static analysis. Also, the database must contain the model geometry data to obtain the eigen value buckling solution.

(4-) Expand the solution

This step is used to review the buckling mode shapes.

(5-) Review the results

It consists of buckling load factors, buckling mode shapes, and relative stress distributions.

The eigenvalue and eigenvector problem needs to be solved for mode-frequency and buckling analyses. It has the form of:

$$[K] \cdot \{\psi_i\} = \lambda_i \cdot [M] \cdot \{\psi_i\}$$

Where

$$[k] = \text{total structure stiffness matrix} = \sum_{m=1}^N [K]^e$$

$\{\psi_i\}$ = ith eigenvector of displacements.

λ_i = ith eigenvalue.

$$[M] = \text{total structure mass matrix} = \sum_{m=1}^N [M]^e$$

N = Number of elements.

$[K]^e$ = element stiffness matrix.

$[M]^e$ = element mass matrix.

For model analyses, the [K] matrix includes the stress stiffness matrix [S]. For eigenvalue buckling analyses, the [M] matrix is replaced with the stress stiffness matrix [S].

Element Selected:

From the ANSYS 5.4 element library the beam 3 (2D-elastic beam) adopted to perform this type of analysis. This element is used to model the column. This element is a uniaxial element with tension, compression, and bending capabilities. The element has three degree of freedom at each node: translations in the nodal x and y directions and rotation about the nodal z-axis. The geometry, node locations and the coordinate system for this element are shown in figure (5).

Results :

The results obtain from experimental work and finite element analyses of the buckling analysis of the composite square beam column are discussed here.

The finite element solution of this problem was based on the following case study:

Case study :

Geometry of the composite column

The square composite column illustrated in figure (2) has the following dimension.

Length (L) = 0.5 m

Width (h) = 0.01 m, 0.015 m, 0.02 m, 0.025 m

Ratio (h/l) = 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05

The square column was made from unidirectional fibrous composite that have different fiber volume fraction ($V_f = 20\%$, 40% , 60% and 80%). Table (1) represent the data of elastic constants at ($V_f = 60\%$) which is based on the rule of mixture for the composite which is based on the constituents properties [18].

Table (2): Results of critical load for composite column.

	Critical Load (N)					
	Glass fiber – Epoxy matrix		Kevlar fiber – Epoxy matrix		Carbon fiber – Epoxy matrix	
	Experimental	F.E.M.	Experimental	F.E.M.	Experimental	F.E.M.
H=0.01 m L=0.5 m H/l=0.02 A=0.0001 m ² I=0.8333*10 ⁻⁹ m ⁴	1310	1480	22000	2500	6333	7238
H=0.015 m L=0.5 m H/l=0.03 A=0.000225 m ² I=4.219*10 ⁻⁹ m ⁴	6521	7495	10950	12658	31511	36641
H=0.02 m L=0.5 m H/l=0.04 A=0.0004 m ² I=13.333*10 ⁻⁹ m ⁴	20371	23687	34204	40005	97854	115803
H=0.025 m L=0.5 m H/l=0.05 A=0.000625 m ² I=32.55*10 ⁻⁹ m ⁴	49156	57830	82530	97668	236074	282723

Figure (6) shows the lateral deflection contours and value of critical load of the composite square beam under a given case study for glass fiber – epoxy matrix, Kevlar fiber – epoxy matrix composite and carbon fiber – epoxy matrix composite.

It is clear from these figures for the column-beam at (h/l = 0.02) that (P_{cr} = 1480 N, 2500 N and 7238 N) for glass fiber – epoxy matrix, Kevlar fiber – epoxy matrix and carbon fiber – epoxy matrix respectively.

While figure (7) shows the first three mode of shape deflection for the buckling analysis for glass fiber-epoxy matrix composite. It is clear from these contours the dangerous one is the first mode of deflection for buckling analysis.

Figures (8- a,b,c and d) show the relationship between critical load and the type of composite material for experimental and finite element analysis at different ratios of (h/l).

These figures show that there are different in the critical load for the finite element analysis and experimental analysis due to the conditions of preparation of the specimens. Where the finite element analysis results was higher than experimental results by the minimum ratio (11.5 %) at (h/l = 0.02) for glass fiber – epoxy matrix composite while by the value (16.5%) at (h/l = 0.05) for carbon fiber- epoxy matrix composite.

Figures (9- a,b and c) illustrate the relationship between critical load and ratio of width to length of column (h/l) for experimental and finite element analysis for glass fiber – epoxy matrix, kevlar fiber – epoxy matrix composite and carbon fiber – epoxy matrix composite respectively.

These figures show the critical load will increase in nonlinear relationship with increase in (h/l) for all types of composite material and for experimental and finite element analysis.

It can be seen that the values of critical load for finite element analysis data higher than the experimental data and this difference increase with increasing (h/l). and the higher value of critical load happen at (h/l = 0.05) for carbon fiber – epoxy matrix composite which is equal to (282723 N), while the lowest value of the critical load happen at (h/l = 0.02) for glass fiber – epoxy matrix composite which is equal to (1480 N).

Figure (10- a and b) show the relationship between critical load (P_{cr}) and the ratio of width to length (h/l) for three different types of composite material and for finite element analysis and for experimental analysis respectively. It can be seen from these figures that the carbon fiber – epoxy matrix composite have the highest value of critical load than glass fiber – epoxy matrix composite.

It was found for the same (h/l) like 0.05 the finite element analysis results higher than the experimental results by the percentage ratio (15 %), (15.5%) and (16.5%) for

Figures (11) show the 3-Dimensional relationship between critical load, fiber volume fraction and various ratios of width to length (h/l) for three different types of composite column.

It is clear from these figures that the critical load (P_{cr}) depend on fiber volume fraction, the ratio (h/l) and material type.

It is illustrated that maximum value of critical load happened at ($V_f = 0.8$) and ($h/l = 0.05$) which is equal to ($P_{cr} = 75.83$ kN, 135.3 kN and 237.1 kN) for glass fiber – epoxy matrix, Kevlar fiber – epoxy matrix and carbon fiber – epoxy matrix respectively.

While the minimum value of critical load happened at ($V_f = 0.2$) and ($h/l = 0.02$) which is equal to ($P_{cr} = 0.541$ kN, 0.925 kN and 1.546 kN) for glass fiber – epoxy matrix, Kevlar fiber – epoxy matrix and carbon fiber – epoxy matrix respectively.

Figures (12 a,b,c and d) show the relationship between critical load and fiber volume fraction for three different material and at different ratios of (h/l).

It is seen from these figures that the critical load increase approximately in linear relationship with increase fiber volume fraction at each value of (h/l) and for each type of composite material.

As shown from figure (12,a) for example at ($V_f = 0.6$) that the ($P_{cr} = 1.48$ kN, 2.599 kN and 4.57 kN) for glass fiber – epoxy matrix, Kevlar fiber – epoxy matrix and carbon fiber – epoxy matrix respectively.

Also found that for the same composite material like glass fiber-epoxy matrix and at ($V_f = 0.4$) the ($P_{cr} = 1.002$ kN, 5.072 kN, 16.028 kN and 39.129 kN) for ($h/l = 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05$) respectively.

Conclusions :

The study of buckling of the square column beam which was made from three different composite materials, different ratios of width to length (h/l), and for different fiber volume fraction involved experimental and finite element analysis.

In this study for determinations of the critical load of the composite square beam, the finite element method was one of the main procedures for this study.

The main conclusions of the present work are:-

(1-) Critical load for finite element analysis was higher than the critical load for experimental work that due to the condition of preparation the specimens. Where the minimum difference was (11.5 %) for glass fiber – epoxy matrix composite at (h/l

= 0.02), while the maximum difference was (16.5 %) for carbon fiber – epoxy matrix composite at ($h/l = 0.05$).

(2-) Ratios of width to length (h/l) of the composite square beam have great effect on buckling analysis for both experimental and finite element analysis. Where with increase (h/l) that lead to increase critical load. Where ($P_{cr} = 1480$ N) at ($h/l = 0.02$) and ($P_{cr} = 57830$ N) at ($h/l = 0.05$) for glass fiber – epoxy matrix composite at ($V_f = 0.6$) for finite element analysis.

(3-) Critical load of buckling analysis depend on the type of composite material, where critical load increase with increase mechanical properties of the composite square column where ($P_{cr} = 1310$ N) for glass fiber – epoxy matrix composite, ($P_{cr} = 2200$ N) for kevelar fiber – epoxy matrix composite, and ($P_{cr} = 6333$ N) for carbon fiber – epoxy matrix composite for the same ($h/l = 0.02$).

(4-) Critical load increase in nonlinear relationship with increase (h/l) for glass fiber – epoxy matrix composite, kevelar fiber – epoxy matrix composite and Carbon fiber – epoxy matrix composite for both experimental and finite element analysis.

(5-) Critical load depends on the fiber volume fraction of the composite where ($P_{cr} = 1480$ N) at ($V_f = 0.6$) and ($P_{cr} = 1002$ N) at ($V_f = 0.4$) for ($h/l = 0.02$) and for glass fiber-epoxy matrix.

(6-) Critical load increases in linear relationship with increase the fiber volume fraction while increase in nonlinear relationship with increase (h/l) for each type of composite material.

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Fig (1) the five stages in the authors failure scenario [11].

Figure (2): Model of the Composite Column

Figure (3): Model of the Hinged Ends Composite Column [12].

Figure (4): Finite Element Model for Half Column [12].

Figure (5): Beam 3 (2-D Elastic Beam) [12].


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ANSYS 5.4
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SMX =.159155

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XF =-.00625
YF =.125
Z-BUFFER
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.025266
.052052
.070726
.088419
.106100
.123787
.141471
.159155
    
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Glass Fiber – Epoxy Matrix
 $h/l = 0.02$
 $V_f = 0.60$
 $P_{cr} = 1480 \text{ N}$


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ANSYS 5.4
JUL 20 2005
06:19:00
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RSYS=0
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SMX =.159155

ZU =1
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XF =-.00625
YF =.125
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Kevlar Fiber – Epoxy Matrix
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 $V_f = 0.60$
 $P_{cr} = 2500 \text{ N}$


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EFACET=1
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XF =-.00625
YF =.125
Z-BUFFER
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.052052
.070726
.088419
.106100
.123787
.141471
.159155
    
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Kevlar Fiber – Epoxy Matrix
 $h/l = 0.02$
 $V_f = 0.60$
 $P_{cr} = 7238 \text{ N}$

Figure (6): Deflection Contours of Three Different Composite Columns.

Figure (7): First Three Mode of Shape Buckling for Glass Fiber – Epoxy Matrix Composite.

(a) at $h/l = 0.02$

(b) at $h/l = 0.03$

(c) at $h/l = 0.04$

(d) at $h/l = 0.05$

Figure (8): Relationship Between Critical Load And Type of Composite Material For Both Experimental And Finite Element Method For Different Ratios of (h/l).

Figure (9): Relationship Between Critical Load and (h/l) for Both Finite Element Method and Experimental Results for
 (a) Glass fiber – Epoxy matrix composite Material.
 (b) Kevlar fiber – Epoxy matrix composite Material.
 (c) Carbon fiber – Epoxy matrix composite Material.

Figure (10): Relationship between Critical load and (h/l) for three different composite material for
 (a) Finite element Method Results.
 (b) Experimental Results.

Figure (11): Relationship Between Critical Load and Fiber Volume Fraction at Different Ratios of (h/l) for:
(a) Glass Fiber – Epoxy Matrix Composite Column.
(b) Kevlar Fiber – Epoxy Matrix Composite Column.
(c) Carbon Fiber – Epoxy Matrix Composite Column.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure (12): Relationship Between Critical Load and Fiber Volume Fraction for Three Different Type of Composite Material at Different Ratios of (h/l):

- (a) $h/l = 0.02$
- (b) $h/l = 0.03$
- (c) $h/l = 0.04$
- (d) $h/l = 0.05$